

Enhancing User Learning in BMI Through Robot Integration

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Abstract—In Brain-machine interfaces (BMIs), users must undergo diligent training to effectively modulate brain rhythms for precise control, a challenge that often results in the moderate performance of BMIs. Traditional BMI setups typically rely on cues and feedback displayed on a screen, which may lack the necessary level of stimulation.

To enhance user learning the integration of real robots into the BMI process is needed. This innovative approach aims to boost user engagement and, consequently, improve the learning experience.

Index Terms—brain-machine interface, user learning, robot applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Brain-Machine Interface (BMI) facilitates communication between an external device and an individual through brain signals [1]. This connection offers the potential to bypass conventional neural pathways, such as muscles and nerves, and establish a new communication channel utilizing brain features, enabling the machine control via users mind.

The user's experience with BMIs can vary depending on the type of brain signals and their acquisition methods (i.e., invasive and non-invasive). In the case of non-invasive methods, electroencephalography (EEG) is the most commonly used signal due to its cost-effectiveness and high temporal resolution [2]. However, its spatial resolution is limited because it relies on electrodes placed on the scalp, which detect the combined activity of many pyramidal neurons located in close proximity to each other [3].

Due to this limitation and the presence of ongoing neuronal activity even during a resting state, EEG data tends to be highly noisy, requiring thorough processing to select relevant features.

Endogenous BMIs rely on the detection of sensorimotor rhythms (SMR) within EEG signals [4]. These rhythms are associated with mental activities and muscular movements, enabling the subject to initiate motor imagery (MI) tasks autonomously, without the need for external stimuli such as visual, auditory, or tactile cues.

Subjects are required to modulate their brain rhythms to transmit precise commands to the actuator. This is not a simple task, and typically, users require extensive training and effort to effectively control the signal features. This difficulty

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contributes to the relatively modest performance of BMIs [5], and it is not always guaranteed that a subject will show improvement over time. When users do not see progress, they may become frustrated and lose motivation, creating a discouraging cycle.

Fig. 1. Example of a visual cue and a feedback presented to the user during a BMI protocol [6]

In conventional BMI protocols, users are typically positioned in front of a monitor displaying cues, such as bars or wheels (Figure 1), which instruct them on what actions to take and how well they are performing. However, this setup may not provide adequate stimulation because the rewards is represented solely by symbols on a screen. Recent studies [7] have explored alternative protocols with the aim of enhancing the user experience and learning during the task.

This work aims to introduce a novel perspective for enhancing user learning in the context of BMIs by incorporating real robots at each stage of the BMI process. The upcoming sections will be dedicated to two key aspects: firstly, the integration of robots into the BMI pipeline, and secondly, methods for assessing and quantifying the user learning.

II. PROTOCOL OVERVIEW

As the literature suggests [8] [9], gamification in BMI has shown the potential to significantly enhance user performance and the perception of this technology. Real-time control of a robot can be viewed as a form of gamification within the process, thanks to its interactive nature and the high level of reward it can provide.

A. Introduction of robot control in BMI

The overall performance of MI-BMI models experiences a significant decline as the number of classes increases [10]. Consequently, fully commanding a robotic device becomes challenging, leading to exceedingly complex control software. This complexity can distract users from their intended motor imagery tasks, further diminishing overall performance. Therefore, it is crucial to delegate low-level commands and details

to the robot's intelligence, allowing the user to focus solely on high-level objectives, such as motor imagery.

To achieve this, shared control approaches (Figure 2) should be employed, enabling user commands to adapt to the environment and efficiently execute robot actions, thus providing robust mental control [11]. Additionally, for a more natural user experience in manipulating the robot, continuous control methods should be utilized instead of the conventional discrete ones [12]. In the discrete approach, BMI outputs accumulate until a threshold is reached before a command is issued. While this method reduces the impact of BMI unreliability on robot control, it significantly decreases the information transfer rate.

Fig. 2. Shared control approach used in BMI with a robotic arm [12]

B. Measuring the user learning

In literature, the evaluation of user improvement and their learning in performing tasks within BMI is often based on metrics such as accuracy in sending commands or similar measures. While this approach provides a quick and convenient way to assess user performance, it should not be the sole criterion for evaluation [13]. It is essential to recognize that accuracy does not always equate to improvement, especially in the long term. One of the fundamental challenges of BMIs and the reason they are primarily studied in controlled environments is their lack of robustness. Performance can vary significantly even within the same day, making them unsuitable for everyday use.

Enhancing the user's ability to modulate brain rhythms and improving this learning process can lead to a more stable, practical, and secure control system [14]. Various measurements of user learning in Euclidean space have been explored, yielding promising results [15] but with certain limitations. Consequently, in recent years, numerous researchers have shifted their focus to alternative spaces, particularly the Riemannian space [16]. This choice is driven by the intriguing characteristics of it, which can also aid in transfer learning between subjects [17], eliminating the need for the initial phase of the BMI pipeline, the model calibration, which consumes a significant amount of time and effort.

III. CONCLUSION

With this work, our aim was to offer innovative ideas for new BMI protocols and provide insights on potential

improvements. We aspire to contribute to the development of more effective controls for real-world scenarios.

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